

Sound-sensing sonoreceptor protein-mediated sonocrine signaling-between biotic and abiotic components

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Understanding how organisms communicate is a fundamental question in biology and is an evolutionarily important milestone. Organisms largely communicate via gas-based gasocrine and light-based photocrine signaling. In addition, organisms also communicate via sound or acoustic waves and sense sound from or generated by abiotic components. However, to the best of my knowledge, there are no specific scientific terms to describe such sound or acoustic wave-mediated organismal communication or sensing of sound from abiotic components. I propose sonocrine signaling to include not only sound-based communication between organisms but also between abiotic components and organisms. The perception of sound may occur not only via specialized sensory organs, but also via sonoreceptors (sound-sensing receptors or mechanoreceptor proteins or mechanosensors or mechanotransduction channels or mechanosensitive proteins). Sonoreceptors include TRP (transient receptor potential) channels such as *Drosophila* NOMPC, NANCHUNG and INACTIVE. Sonoreceptors may also include other mechanosensitive channels (MscL, MscS, stretch-activated Ca²⁺-permeable channels etc.) in microorganisms and plants. Difference in sonoreceptors expression and/or activity may explain hypersensitivity to sound in some animals and may provide an evolutionary benefit for the individual organism or the community.